

Anton Paar Kaomi for Nova

version 1.01
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Report date: 09/04/2025 Operator: admin
File Name: AA_TB-DAPB page 167_CO2 273K.qcuPhysIso

Analysis Information

Sample	ID	AA_TB-DAPB pag	Weight	0.11g	Description	AA_TB-DAPB page 167_CO2
Analysis	Data ID	{c1a417e9-2042-4276-86d7-c2ffe9b4ed1f}	Date	2022/09/15	Duration	0.00min
	Operator	quantachrome	Station ID	A	Firmware	0.00
	Instrument	NOVA	p₀ Mode		Cell ID	79
	Ambient Temp.	-273.16°C			Thermal Delay	600sec
	Cell Volume	0				
Adsorbate	Name	Carbon-dioxide	Molecular Weight	0g/mol	Cross Sectional Area	0Å ² /molecule
	Non-Ideality	0 _{1/Torr}	Bath Temperature	273.15K		
Degassing	Degas Time	0.0hrs	Degas Temperature	0.0°C		

Data Reduction Parameters

Thermal Transpiration	yes	Eff. Molec. Diameter	3.54Å			
Eff. Cell Diameter	4mm					
Adsorbate Model	Name	Carbon Dioxide	Molecular Weight	44.0095g/mol	Cross Sectional Area	21Å ² /molecule
	Bath Temperature	273.15K				

BET Multipoint BET Results

Isotherm Branch	Adsorption
Slope	14.7163
Intercept	0.456236
Correlation coeff., r	0.999362
C constant	33.2559
Surface area	189.391 m ² /g

Table - BET Multipoint BET

Relative Pressure, p/p ₀	Volume Adsorbed @STP cm ³ /g	1 / [W((p ₀ /p) - 1)]
0.0255927	16.0755	0.8321
0.0264997	16.3893	0.8459
0.0273747	16.6841	0.8592
0.0283743	16.9909	0.8753
0.0292113	17.2833	0.8867
0.0301528	17.5840	0.9005
0.0308992	17.8571	0.9094